

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

EVALUATION OF LONG-TERM RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF IATROGENIC INJURIES OF THE URETER

1. **Oripov Rustam Anvarovich** - Samarkand State University Department of Skin and Venereal Diseases Samarkand, Uzbekistan
2. **Karimov Kuvonchbek Ravshan ogli** - student of Samarkand State University
3. **Parmanova Aziza Javlonovna** - student of Samarkand State University

Annotation: This article provides information about a study of 99 women aged 19 to 65 years with a history of iatrogenic ureteral injuries after obstetric and gynecological operations. The aim of our work was to evaluate the long-term results of the treatment of iatrogenic ureteral injuries. To study the effect of body mass index on the incidence of iatrogenic ureteral injuries.

Key words: treatment, iatrogenic injuries of the ureter

Relevance. In peacetime, it is extremely rare. Injury to the ureter is often combined with damage to the kidney or other adjacent organs. In clinical practice, there is an accidental, iatrogenic violation of the integrity of the ureter in obstetric, gynecological and urological practice during surgery on the organs of the abdominal cavity, retroperitoneal space and small pelvis [1].

If damage to the ureter is suspected, emergency hospitalization for surgical treatment is indicated. In the case of a combined injury, shock and internal bleeding are possible - the introduction of antishock and hemostatic agents at the prehospital stage is indicated.

Iatrogenic damage to the upper urinary tract is one of the most serious complications of various surgical interventions on the organs of the abdominal

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

cavity, retroperitoneal space and small pelvis. The frequency of intraoperative damage to the ureter during obstetric and gynecological operations ranges from 1 to 5%, and increases to 15-20% in oncological pathology. The development of these complications is facilitated, on the one hand, by the anatomically close location of the distal ureter to the internal genital organs, and, on the other hand, by their altered topographic and anatomical ratio in pathological conditions. It is also worth noting that the widespread introduction of endoscopic and endovideosurgical methods of treatment into medical practice and the expansion of indications for radical oncological operations have led to an increase in the number of patients with iatrogenic injuries of the ureters.

Objective: To evaluate the long-term results of treatment of iatrogenic ureteral injuries. To study the effect of body mass index on the incidence of iatrogenic ureteral injuries. Establish the structure of surgical interventions, in which the ureters are most often damaged. Determine the timing of establishing the diagnosis of iatrogenic damage to the ureter in the study group.

Materials and methods. For 10 years in the clinic, about 99 women aged 19 to 65 years with iatrogenic injuries of the ureter after obstetric and gynecological operations in history. This number did not include women in whom the diagnosis of iatrogenic ureteral injury was established on the operating table or in the first 4 days after the primary operation. In addition to routine research methods, to clarify the localization of damage to the ureter and its extent, methods such as ascending ureteropyelography were used, in the presence of a nephrostomy - retrograde pyeloureterography, excretory urography.

Results and its discussion. We analyzed data on body mass index in patients with

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

iatrogenic ureteral injury. It was found that 61.6% of women were overweight, 30.3% of patients had a body mass index within the normal range, and 8.1% of patients had a body mass deficiency. We have studied the nature of operations in patients with iatrogenic damage to the ureter and established the main surgical interventions in which the ureters are most often injured. In 43 cases, iatrogenic damage to the ureter occurred during supravaginal amputation of the uterus for fibromyoma; in 38 cases, this happened during radical and extended operations for cervical tumors from the transabdominal access; in 17 cases, during surgical interventions for tumors, ovarian cysts and appendages. There was also one case of iatrogenic damage to the ureter during caesarean section in the lower uterine segment, followed by amputation of the uterus due to bleeding. Based on the history data and available medical documentation, we studied the timing of the establishment of iatrogenic damage to the ureter in the study group. In 30% of patients, iatrogenic damage to the ureter was diagnosed on days 5-14, in 38.4% of patients - in the period of 15 days -1 month, in 31.3% of women - in a period of one to three months. The main and prevailing complications in iatrogenic damage to the urinary tract were ureteral obstruction and urogenital fistulas (92.3%). All patients with iatrogenic injuries of the ureter underwent surgical treatment. The structure of operations performed: according to Boari - 19, direct ureteroneocystoanastomosis - 20, ureteroneocystoanastomosis with antireflux protection - 36, ureteroureteroanastomosis - 11, intestinal ureteroplasty - 1, nephroureterectomy - 12.

Conclusions: an increase in body mass index has a direct effect on the frequency of poolic damage to the ureter. 61% of patients had a state of gress (BMI 25-30) or obesity of the I-II degree (BMI 30-40). Injuries of the ureter most often occur

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/>
реестр:1070589

during supravaginal amputation of the uterus for fibromyoma - 43 cases, and during radical and extended operations for cervical tumors from the transabdominal access - 38 cases. In the majority (68/99) of the patients in the study group, the diagnosis of iatrogenic ureteral injury was belated. This confirms the fact of insufficient awareness of obstetrician-gynecologists about the anatomical and topographic features of the lower third of the ureter, since the results of treatment of patients with complications of iatrogenic injuries of the urinary tract depend on the timing of the diagnosis from the moment of injury and the timely adoption of urgent measures for decompression of the upper urinary tract.

Literature:

1. Dobrowolski Z, Kusionowicz J, Drewniak T, Habrat W, Lipczyński W, Jakubik P, Węglarz W. Renal and ureteric trauma: diagnosis and management in Poland. // BJU Int. 2002. Vol. 89, N 7. P. 748-751.
2. Elliott SP, McAninch JW. Ureteral injuries: external and iatrogenic // Urol Clin North Am. 2006. Vol. 33, N 1. P. 55-66.
3. Visco AG, Taber KH, Weidner AC, Barber MD, Myers ER. Cost-effectiveness of universal cystoscopy to identify ureteral injury at hysterectomy. // Obstet Gynecol. 2001. Vol. 97, N 5, Pt. 1. P. 685-692.
4. Лебедев М.А. Хирургическое лечение ятрогенных повреждений мочевыводящих путей и их осложнений: Дис. ... канд. мед. наук. СПб., 2008. 186 с.
5. Аблакулова М., Хусинова Ш., Юлдашова Н. Качество жизни и хроническая сердечная недостаточность // Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 171-179.
6. Хусинова Ш., Аблакулова М., Хакимова Л. Процесс рационального назначения лекарственных средств и выбор персонального лекарства в

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/>
реестр:1070589

практике ВОП //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 683-689.

7. Хусинова Ш. Качество ведения больных хронической сердечной недостаточностью в первичном звене здравоохранения //Журнал кардиореспираторных исследований. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 99-102.

8. Ахмедова М. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОНИХОМИКОЗОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-190.

9. Тошев С. У., Аширов З. Ф., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВИТИЛИГО 308-нм ЭКСИМЕРНЫМ ЛАЗЕРОМ //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2021. – С. 240-243.

10. Нарзикулов Р. и др. Клинико-эпидемиологическая характеристика больных гонореей женщин в самаркандской области //Журнал вестник врача. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 93-98.

11. Хусинова Ш., Аблакулова М., Хакимова Л. Процесс рационального назначения лекарственных средств и выбор персонального лекарства в практике ВОП //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 683-689.

12. Хакимова Л., Лапасова Ф. Роль дистанционного обучения в системе высшего образования в период карантинных мероприятий в связи с пандемией Covid-19 //InterConf. – 2020.

13. Аблакулова М., Хусинова Ш., Юлдашова Н. Качество жизни и хроническая сердечная недостаточность //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 171-179.

14. Рахимова Х. М. и др. Современные аспекты по улучшению качества

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/>
реестр:1070589

ведения больных с патологией эндокринных органов в условиях первичного звена медицинской помощи //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 10 (51). – С. 74-77.

15. Рахимова Х. М. и др. Современные аспекты по улучшению качества ведения больных с патологией эндокринных органов в условиях первичного звена медицинской помощи //Достижения науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 10 (51). – С. 74-77.

16. Хакимова Л. и др. Безопасное материнство и эффективный антенатальный уход //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8/S. – С. 91-95.

17. Аблакулова М., Хусинова Ш., Юлдашова Н. Качество жизни и хроническая сердечная недостаточность //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 171-179.

18. Аблакулова М. Х., Хусинова Ш. А., Юлдашова Н. Э. РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОСТЬ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ СЕРДЦА В ГОРОДСКОЙ НЕОРГАНИЗОВАННОЙ ПОПУЛЯЦИИ ГОРОДА САМАРКАНДА //Журнал кардиореспираторных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1.

19. Касьянов Г. И. и др. Инновационная технология стерилизации плодового и овощного сырья //Доклады Российской академии сельскохозяйственных наук. – Некоммерческая организация Редакция журнала " Доклады Российской академии сельскохозяйственных наук", 2014. – №. 6. – С. 57-59.

20. Абдуллаев Д. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КРЕМАТЕРБИЗИЛ ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ МИКОЗОВ

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

//BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 181-185.

